

Deliverable D9.4

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1. Executive summary

We have developed a software pipeline, named SMaSB, to perform automated volume/shape matching (Deliverable D9.1). Together with a database of over 1000 volumes from the Electron Microscopy Data Bank (EMDB) and Protein Data Bank (PDB), the pipeline underpins a web service PDBeShape (Deliverable 9.2). Deliverable 9.3 implemented automated and manual segmentation into the PDBeShape web service.

A segment-level description of volume data allows a precise annotation of multi-component complexes, linking out to relevant bioinformatics resources. However, a given protein component, described by a single UniProt ID, may adopt different conformations in different complexes reflecting its particular function in each complex. The resolution of volume data does not always allow the precise conformation to be determined, although it may limit the possibilities. It is therefore appropriate to include a level of structural annotation.

In this deliverable, we use an analysis technique developed for NMR and SAXS data to provide structural annotation for components in the PDBeShape volume database. The output is a set of conformations that a protein component can adopt, and that are consistent with the volume data. The approach utilises multiple data sources for structural biology. As more structural biology data is collected, the range of conformations that are possible can be narrowed, and the structural annotation updated.

2. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Develop a database of annotated bio macromolecular volume data	X	
2	Develop software to search this database using atomic or volume data	X	
3	Methods for routine updates developed	X	

4	methods to identify components (“segments”) and annotate them implemented	X	
5	Integration of SAXS and NMR data on flexible proteins in solution	X	
6	Tools available via webserver	X	

3. Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

Work Package 9 aims to introduce appropriate descriptors of the mobility of proteins and their complexes into structural databases. Protein mobility occurs over an extensive range of timescales and structural levels. Local, fast mobility has been already extensively addressed in the scientific literature. NMR spectroscopy allows the direct measurement of protein flexibility through so-called nuclear relaxation measurements. These data can be interpreted using different physical models and report on the motions affecting individual chemical groups within each amino acid of the protein. The most common framework of analysis is the model-free formalism ¹. Order parameters derived using this formalism can be deposited to the BioMagResBank (<http://www.bmrb.wisc.edu/>) ². Related information can also be obtained from the interpretation of B-factors in X-ray diffraction experiments. Although the latter is not a direct measure of mobility, there is often a good correlation between information derived from X-ray and NMR data ³.

On the other hand, motions that involve larger portions of the overall protein structure are harder to characterize experimentally and there is no consensus in the scientific literature in terms of the physical models for their interpretation. Combination of experimental data from different structural techniques are required for the determination of dynamic features based on the combined analysis of independent data types. Within the present work package we developed a tool to estimate the probability of various conformations in multi-domain proteins, through the integration of NMR and SAXS (Small-Angle X-ray Scattering) data. We additionally evaluated the feasibility and usefulness of using the output of the present tool to support the interpretation of volume data

performed by PDBeShape, based on a calmodulin test case. PDBeShape was described in D9.2. In doing so, we identified the most useful metadata to capture the type of protein motions investigated by the tool, for future inclusion in structural databases.

3.2 *MaxOcc and MaxOR*

Our approach integrates different types of NMR data (diamagnetic and paramagnetic, the latter depending on the presence of unpaired electrons in the investigated system) and SAXS data. This is an extension over the original concept, which exploited only paramagnetic NMR data. In general, the equations describing the experimental data in terms of the conformational equilibria existing in the protein system admit an infinite number of solutions. The approach implemented seeks to recover the minimum, i.e. including the lowest number of different conformations, ensemble (sparsest solution) that satisfies the experimental observables⁴⁻⁷. Within this frame, we defined two crucial parameters:

1. The maximum occurrence (**MaxOcc**) of each and every conformer. it is defined as the maximum weight that it can obtain when part of a conformational ensemble without violating the constraints of the experimental data. No restriction is posed on the number of conformations to be included in the ensemble. Maximum occurrence (MaxOcc) can be interpreted as the maximum fraction of time that a conformation can exist, when taken together with any ensemble of conformations with optimized weights.
2. The upper limit for the occurrence of all conformations in a given region of the entire conformational space (**MaxOR**). It corresponds to the maximum percent of time, respectively, that the protein can spend in any ensemble of conformations belonging to a defined region and still be in agreement with the experimental data. The above definition of MaxOR allows also the calculation of the minimum occurrence of a region (**minOR**) from the difference between 1.00 and the maxOR of the complementary region. This definition was elaborated ⁴ in the previous

year of activity of the present WP, as described also in the previous periodic report.

MaxOcc calculations (as well as rigid body minimization in the case of very limited mobility) can accurately point out which individual conformations are in best agreement with the experimental data, although they may still be unable to fully reproduce the data. However, MaxOcc values alone do not provide information on the size of the conformational region sampled by the protein. To gain a deeper insight into the extent of the mobility, one should calculate the maxOR of the region defined by the conformations structurally close to the highest MaxOcc conformation. The size of the smallest region in the conformational space that can reproduce the data completely (i.e., with maxOR = 1) can be regarded as a lower bound to the extent of the residual mobility (Figure 1A). By the same token, the minimum occurrence of a region (minOR) is the minimum percent of time that a system must spend in a given set of conformations when included in any optimized ensemble, to allow for fitting of the experimental data (Figure 1B). A large minimum occurrence for a region that also has high maxOR rules out the possibility that the corresponding structures are the accidental outcome of the motional averaging between other different conformations.

Figure 1: regions of conformational space corresponding to values of the maxOR and minOR parameters

Based on the above concepts, it is possible to identify cases where e.g. two different, largely separated conformational states are in equilibrium by analysing and computing MaxOcc and MaxOR values for combinations of regions of conformational space, rather than for individual regions.

The maintenance and possible further extension of the software integrating the MaxOcc and MaxOR methodologies will be guaranteed within the Virtual Research Environment (VRE) initiative called West-Life (<https://www.west-life.eu/>). West-Life involves all the partners of the present WP.

3.3 Calmodulin as a test system for the integration of MaxOcc output into PDBeShape

Calmodulin (CaM) is a 16 kDa, highly conserved protein, implicated in many biological functions. It is composed of two very similar domains (N- and C-terminal domains), connected by a linker. Each domain is composed of two EF-hand motifs (helix-loop-helix motifs), and can bind up to 2 calcium (II) ions, so that the full length protein can bind up to 4 calcium(II) ions. After calcium binding, the relative orientation of the two helices of the EF-hand motifs changes, passing from a roughly antiparallel arrangement (closed, or parallel bundle, form) to an almost perpendicular arrangement (open, or orthogonal bundle, form). The calcium form exposes a large part of the hydrophobic core, and the resulting hydrophobic cavity is a very good binder for α -helical motifs present in a variety of target proteins. In essence, an increase in intracellular calcium concentration triggers the EF-hand domains into their open form, which in turn binds a target protein and activates a biological response.

Whereas the N-terminal and C-terminal domains have rigid structures, they can rearrange freely with respect to one another, when the protein is free in solution, because they are connected by a flexible linker. Solving the CaM structure thus requires the definition of the relative position of the two domains. This high degree of flexibility of the interdomain linker is of course absent in the solid state. Actually, X-ray structures of the calcium(II)-loaded CaM suggested that the last helix of the N-terminal domain, the first helix of the C-terminal domain and the interdomain linker constitute a long continuous helix. Such conformation is inconsistent with NMR data in solution, which showed a very high degree of mobility of residues 78-81 in the interdomain linker, indicating that the helical structure in such region is disrupted. Remarkably, a crystal structure was also obtained in which the two domains touch one another. **Interdomain flexibility is the basis of the functionally relevant role of CaM**, for which a large number

of binding partners have been identified. The formation of complexes induces CaM to assume a compact conformation, and depending on the specific binding interactions, the mobility between the two domains can be reduced to different extents, ranging from still very flexible up to almost complete relative immobilization.

Thus CaM is a very relevant test case, in which protein motion is closely linked to its physiological functional role. Two EM structures of calmodulin bound to protein structures are available from the EM databank, which permits testing of the use of MaxOcc output in the analysis of the EM data. EMD-5940 is a 23Å resolution cryoEM volume for mammalian neuronal nitric oxide synthase in complex with calmodulin which drives the release of the FMN domain. EMD-5679 is a 25Å resolution cryoEM volume for an aquaporin-0/calmodulin complex, in which Ca²⁺-calmodulin is responsible for water-channel gating. In both cases, the approximate position of calmodulin in the complex is known, but no conformational details are available at this resolution.

3.4 Integration of MaxOcc output into PDBeShape

For the present proof-of-concept of the possible integration of the MaxOcc output into PDBeShape, we did the following:

1. Based on the calmodulin NMR and SAXS datasets described in our previous work^{4,6}, we selected all the structures with MaxOcc values in the top range of the distribution generated for 50,000 random conformations
2. The structures from step #1 were clustered based on the RMSD of the coordinates of the second (C-terminal) domain after superimposition of the first (N-terminal) domain. This resulted in three clusters.
3. For each cluster of step #2, one central structure was taken as representative of the cluster, with a weight defined by the MaxOcc/MaxOR procedure outlined in section 3.2
4. The coordinates of the three representative structures of step #3 were used as input to identify the position of CaM in the EM maps

Unfortunately, the low resolution of the available EM maps (more than 20 Å) prevented us from effectively discriminating the different configurations provided by the MaxOcc analysis in the volumes. Model fitting algorithms often failed to locate the known location of calmodulin in the full volumes of the complexes. When the search was restricted to the known location (see the segmentation in Figure 2), the conformations from MaxOcc could be fitted, but still did not give consistent orientations or scores for the different conformations. In this case, all conformations are included in the structural annotation.

Figure 2: Segmentation of EMD-5940. The segment in brown corresponds reasonably well with the proposed location of CaM.

In future work related to the topics addressed in this WP, we foresee the following. After the successful implementation of automatic segmentation of all the volumes in the database developed in the course of BioMedBridges, the generated segments will be annotated according to their likely contents. In an ideal case, it will say segment 17 of volume 203 corresponds to a given Uniprot entry. When available, the annotation will include known atomic-level 3D structures. For systems where MaxOcc analyses are available, a further addition to the annotation will be MaxOcc conformations, selected as outlined above. This will indicate to the users the extent of conformational heterogeneity that might be applicable to this segment (regardless of the resolution of the EM map). With sufficient resolution of the EM map, so that model fitting discriminates between atomic models, it may become possible to reject some of the possible conformations.

Regarding the metadata to associate to MaxOcc conformations within the database, the following are most relevant:

- Type of input data used to generate the conformations
- Number of conformations generated
- Number of representative conformations selected
- MaxOR and MinOR parameters for cluster regions around the representative conformation.

In the current implementation, the PDBeShape volume database contains a link to a file of MaxOcc results. In future versions, the schema will be updated to include segment-level annotations, and this will include details of possible models such as MaxOcc conformations. Update of the schema is now linked to international efforts to develop a data model for segmentation (see Deliverable 9.3).

4. References

- (1) Lipari, G., Szabo, A. (1982) Model-free approach to the interpretation of nuclear magnetic resonance relaxation in macromolecules. 2. Analysis of experimental results. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 104, 4559-4570.
- (2) Ulrich, E. L., Akutsu, H., Doreleijers, J. F., Harano, Y., Ioannidis, Y. E., Lin, J., Livny, M., Mading, S., Maziuk, D., Miller, Z., Nakatani, E., Schulte, C. F., Tolmie, D. E., Wenger, R. K., Yao, H., Markley, J. L. (2008) BioMagResBank. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 36, D402-D408.
- (3) Bertini, I., Calderone, V., Cosenza, M., Fragai, M., Lee, Y.-M., Luchinat, C., Mangani, S., Terni, B., Turano, P. (2005) Conformational variability of MMPs: beyond a single 3D structure. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 102, 5334-5339.
- (4) Andralojc, W., Luchinat, C., Parigi, G., Ravera, E. (2014) Exploring regions of conformational space occupied by two-domain proteins. *J. Phys. Chem. B* 118, 10576-10587.
- (5) Bertini, I., Giachetti, A., Luchinat, C., Parigi, G., Petoukhov, M. V., Pierattelli, R., Ravera, E., Svergun, D. I. (2010) Conformational space of

flexible biological macromolecules from average data. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 132, 13553-13558.

(6) Bertini, I., Ferella, L., Luchinat, C., Parigi, G., Petoukhov, M. V., Ravera, E., Rosato, A., Svergun, D. I. (2012) MaxOcc: a web portal for Maximum Occurrence Analysis. *J. Biomol. NMR* 53, 271-280.

(7) Andralojc, W., Berlin, K., Fushman, D., Luchinat, C., Parigi, G., Ravera, E., Sgheri, L. (2015) Information content of long-range NMR data for the characterization of conformational heterogeneity. *J. Biomol. NMR* 62, 353-371.

5. Delivery and schedule

This deliverable has been completed according to schedule

6. Adjustments made

None

7. Background information

This deliverable relates to WP 9; background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of work (DoW) is included below.

WP 9 Title: Use case: From cells to molecules- integrating structural data
 Lead: Martyn Winn (STFC)
 Participants: EMBL, STFC, CIRMMMP

Work package number	WP9	Start date or starting event:	month 13	
Work package title	From cells to molecules- integrating structural data			
Activity Type	RTD			
Participant number	1: EMBL	4: STFC	20: CIRMMMP	
Person-months per participant	32	33	8	

Objectives

We will develop tools (software, database, web-based services) to bridge the resolution ranges encountered in atomic, molecular and cellular structural biology. Specifically, we will:

1. Develop a database of annotated biomacromolecular volume data (derived from PDB and EMDB and annotated by UniProt and other relevant database identifiers) and software to search this database using atomic or volume data that result from experimental structure determinations. These tools will be made available through a webserver. Methods will be developed to routinely update the database with every new release of PDB and EMDB.
2. Implement methods to identify components (“segments”) and annotate them (using UniProt and other relevant database identifiers) in experimentally determined volume data (e.g., tomograms). This functionality will be made available as a webserver and will possibly be integrated in the deposition procedures for EMDB/PDB.
3. Integration of SAXS and NMR data on flexible proteins in solution in order to evaluate the average shapes, as well as the shapes of the various conformations sampled in solution.

Task 1. (STFC, EMBL)

Structural biology is producing unprecedented amounts of structural data that increase not only in number, but also in size and complexity and that span an ever-wider range of resolutions. Whereas X-ray crystallography and NMR spectroscopy produce structural models with atomic detail, techniques such as 3D cryo-Electron Microscopy and Tomography as well as Small-Angle Scattering (X-ray and neutrons) produce lower-resolution volume and shape data. Moreover, a deluge of hybrid techniques currently being developed is expected to produce complex mixtures of high-resolution and low-resolution structural information about ever more complex molecular machines. Whereas there are very good bioinformatics tools available for the analysis, validation and comparison of atomic structures, at present there are very few tools available that deal with low-resolution data (i.e., volume or shape data). In this task, we will address this by developing tools (software, database, web-based services) for searching the structural archive, not at the level of atoms or secondary structure elements (for which good tools are available, some of which were developed jointly by partners now involved in INSTRUCT and ELIXIR), but based on shape (volume data). The shape database will be derived from the holdings of PDB and EMDB and will contain annotated shape data at various level of resolution. The shape-matching software will be able to take structural data (be it an atomic model or volume data itself) and compare it to the contents of the shape database in order to identify known structures with similar shape or with a component of similar shape. Such software will be invaluable to assist in annotation of, for instance, whole-cell tomograms and for identification of components of known structure or shape in large multi-molecule complexes. The software will be made available both stand-alone and as a web-server. Methods will be developed to routinely update the shape database with every new release of PDB and EMDB.

Task 2. (EMBL, STFC)

The second task focuses on delineation, identification and annotation of segments in experimentally determined volume data (single-particle reconstructions, tomograms, possibly small-angle scattering). At present, volume data can be deposited in EMDB without any link to atomic structures, either because the structures are not yet known or because the authors of the study choose not to fit existing structures or to deposit them. The value of the EMDB archive would be enhanced substantially if volume data would be decomposed into its constituent bio macromolecular components (various proteins, possibly RNA or DNA, etc.) and identified through annotation using UniProt and other relevant database identifiers. We will examine and adapt existing segmentation software so that it can be incorporated into the annotation tool. The annotation tool itself will be developed initially as a stand-alone web-server. It will also be considered for integration in the EMDB/PDB deposition pipelines, in consultation with the international partners in those two organisations. The two tasks together will result in significant new functionality that will aid:

- (structural) biologists who want to find out if a certain bio macromolecular structure has the same shape as a known structure (which may be known at atomic level or as part of an experimentally determined volume, such as an EM map or tomogram);
- (structural) biologists who want to interpret complex volume data in terms of possible and plausible structures of components of that data (e.g., when annotating particles in a tomogram);

- PDB/EMDB in the sense that previously deposited volumes for which no atomic data was available can be scanned regularly for fits of newly determined structures. Moreover, once segmentation and identification information is available, whenever an atomic structure becomes available for a component that was previously only known at the level of its shape, this information can be exploited automatically and the structure can be fit into the volume data. This will transform EMDB from a static archive of volume data, to a dynamic archive whose content will continue to develop and become richer as time goes by and new atomic structures become available.

Task 3. (CIRMMP, STFC, EMBL)

The third task relates to proteins which experience some kind of mobility in solution, and to how this mobility can become a descriptor in structural databases. The task consists of finalizing programs available and partly developed by CIRMMP to determine the shape of the various protein conformations sampled in solution and, according to their estimated statistical weight, to determine selected measurable properties. The programs will take advantage of experimental parameters mainly from NMR and SAXS. Once finalized, the programs will be integrated with the shape-matching software and service of Task 1.